

Synthesis of a New Series of Chromonyl Chalcones

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The α,β -unsaturated ketones (2 and 4) were prepared by the condensation of 3-formylchromone (1) or 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-2,3-dimethylchromone (3) with substituted-acetophenones or different aromatic aldehydes. Structures of the compounds were established by their analytical and spectral data.

THE α,β -unsaturated ketones are important and versatile intermediates for the preparation of various heterocycles. Keeping this in view and in continuation of our work^{1,2} on chromone systems, we report a novel synthesis of hitherto unknown chromonyl chalcones.

3-Formylchromone* (1) was reacted with different substituted acetophenones in alcoholic potassium hydroxide to give 3-(3-aryl-3-oxo-1-propenyl)-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (2) in good yields; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 680 (O=C-C) and 1 635 cm^{-1} (pyronyl C=O). With a slight variation in the workup, condensation of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-2,3-dimethylchromone* (3) with different aromatic aldehydes yielded a few new chalcones, 8-(3-aryl-1-oxo-2-propen-1-yl)-7-hydroxy-2,3-dimethyl-4H-1-benzopyran-4-ones (4) (Scheme 1); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 350 (chelated OH) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=O). All the chalcones have been charac-

terised by their analytical and spectral characteristics.

Scheme 1

In the pmr spectrum of 2a, the α and β protons of chalcone system absorbed at δ 7.0 and 7.9

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF CHALCONES*

Compd. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	H
2a	Phenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₂	166	70	78.00 (78.19)	4.12 (4.34)
2b	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClO ₂	169	74	69.45 (69.56)	3.45 (3.49)
2c	p-Tolyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₂	175	72	78.48 (78.62)	4.69 (4.82)
2d	p-Methoxyphenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	148	76	74.21 (74.48)	4.32 (4.57)
4a	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄	185	58	74.86 (75.00)	4.91 (5.00)
4b	p-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ ClO ₄	156	60	67.44 (67.68)	4.16 (4.23)
4c	p-Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄	162	72	75.21 (75.44)	5.18 (5.39)
4d	o-Chlorophenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ ClO ₄	193	77	67.52 (67.68)	4.11 (4.23)
4e	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆	187	62	69.26 (69.47)	5.18 (5.26)
4f	p-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₅	183	66	71.78 (71.99)	4.72 (4.85)
4g	p-Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ NO ₄	198	61	72.63 (72.72)	5.67 (5.78)
4h	o-Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₅	207	58	71.08 (71.42)	4.61 (4.76)
4i	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₅	202	57	74.46 (74.61)	4.51 (4.66)

*Analyses for Cl and N found satisfactory.

appearing as a pair of doublets (J 9Hz). The hydrogen attached to C-2 of chromone nucleus appeared as a singlet at δ 8.2. All other aromatic protons displayed a complex multiplet pattern in the region δ 7.2–8.0. A three-proton singlet at δ 2.0 of **4c** was due to the methyl group present on the phenyl nucleus. The two methyl groups attached to chromone nucleus appeared together at δ 2.33. The two doublets situated at δ 6.6 and 7.9 are assigned to α and β hydrogens of chalcone system (J 9Hz). The hydrogens of *p*-disubstituted-phenyl ring system appeared as two doublets at δ 6.9 and 7.2 (J_{AB} 7.5Hz). The other two aromatic hydrogens of chromone system absorbed at δ 7.6 and 7.8. The chelated hydroxylic proton appeared as a singlet at δ 10.3.

Experimental

Melting points were uncorrected. Ir spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (90 MHz) on a Varian A-90 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. The physical and analytical data are given in Table 1.

α,β -Unsaturated ketones (2, 4) : Equimolar (0.01 mol) mixture of the appropriate ketone and alde-

hyde was dissolved in methanol (40 ml), and potassium hydroxide (5 g) was added to it. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h and kept overnight at room temperature. It was then poured over crushed ice with stirring and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid separated was filtered, washed and dried. All the chalcones obtained were purified from alcohol as shining coloured crystals.

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